

China And Vietnam Beliefs Fusion In Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

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Abstract

The article presents the religious characteristics of the Chinese people and the fusion of Chinese and Vietnamese beliefs in the process of community living in the most dynamic developing of Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. The Chinese settled in Saigon (Ho Chi Minh City) around the end of the seventeenth century, mainly as part of the failed "Anti-Qing sentiment" movement that fled to Southeast Asia and located in the area of Bien Hoa, My Tho. The fluctuations of the situation in Vietnam at the end of the 18th century led the Chinese people to gradually leave other centers and focus on living in Saigon (Ho Chi Minh City), turning this place into the largest Chinese settlement center in the South as well as in Vietnam. When the Chinese came here, the Vietnamese were here before, they lived together, explored the land, traded... The process of cultural interference took place, especially in beliefs fusion, the process of fusion formed a very unique feature of the Chinese in Ho Chi Minh City compared to other localities.

Introduction

Belief is a historical phenomenon in the spiritual field of social life. There are thousands of different types of beliefs in the world, very rich and diverse. The Chinese who immigrated to Vietnam from China brought with them a lot of religious consciousness from their homeland, and integrated in the new land, along with the indigenous communities, especially the Vietnamese, to create a unique religious belief system. In particular, these forms are clearly shown in Ho Chi Minh City. The Chinese as well as the Vietnamese believe in a soul and believe in animism. Therefore, the Chinese in the Ho Chi Minh City area have actively worshiped many gods residing in different realms to pray for much support. Based on studies and surveys, it is possible to consider the process of merging Chinese and Vietnamese beliefs in terms of: outside community life and inside the family. The process of coexistence between the Vietnamese and the Chinese for more than 300 years has formed many forms of cultural exchange in the beliefs of the Chinese, demonstrating the integration process of the Chinese community into the Vietnamese community. These manifestations can be seen in many forms: architecture, decoration, rituals, worshiped gods, offerings, festivals, etc., and especially in ancestor worship. The article presents the religious characteristics of the Chinese people and the fusion of Chinese and Vietnamese beliefs in the process of community living in the most dynamic developing of Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.

Literature Review

Regarding the topic of the article, there are works of domestic and international scientists such as: "*Chinese in South Vietnam*" by Tsai Maw Kuey not only deals with economic activities but also presents aspects related to the Chinese community in South Vietnam: it refers to the immigration of Chinese people. The Chinese entered South Vietnam before the French colonial period to form the urban areas of Ha Tien, Cho Lon and the states; immigration when the French invaded Vietnam. Among them, it is noteworthy that the cohesion by locality and dialect, forming the states of the Cantonese, Chaozhou, Fujian, Hei and Hainan groups, associated with the existence of these groups with the community facilities such as hospitals, cemeteries, schools, libraries. The Chinese society in Saigon reflects the religious and belief life here.

Phan Xuan Bien, Phan An with the study "*On the position of the Chinese in the Vietnamese ethnic community*" shows that the organizational process of the Chinese community has integrated into the Vietnamese social community, attached to the Vietnamese community. Vietnam's homeland, all economic and social changes, class analysis among people have been influenced by Vietnamese society over the periods.

The book "*Chinese people in District 6, Ho Chi Minh City*" edited by Phan An, however, only mentions the Chinese in one location, but has provided a lot of valuable information for the article. District 6 of Ho Chi Minh City is home to a relatively large concentration of Chinese people, most of whom were born in Vietnam, and very few people migrated from China. The residence of the Chinese in District 6 is mainly concentrated in busy

markets (such as Binh Tay market, Minh Phung market, Gia Phu market...). This is also the place that shows the fusion of Chinese and Vietnamese beliefs in Ho Chi Minh City most clearly.

"*Geographical and historical developments in the process of cultural contact and exchange between Vietnam and China*" by Chau Thi Hai gave an overview of the geographical and historical developments in the process of cultural contact and exchange between China and Vietnam. Vietnamese and Chinese imprints in Southeast Asian art and culture and focusing on understanding the role of the Chinese people in cultural transmission in Vietnam, highlighting the characteristics of the Sino-Vietnamese integration and its manifestations. specifics of that integration on the fields, culture, architecture, art, shaping, in the development of craft industries. This is the basis for the author to compare the fusion of Chinese-Vietnamese beliefs in Ho Chi Minh City with the general context of Southeast Asia.

Ly Tung Hieu, in the article "*Overview of the religion of Southern residents*", said that the Chinese possess a very diverse divine system. Corresponding to that divine system is the system of worship facilities which is also very rich. Referring to the beliefs of the Chinese people in the South, the most important part must be the objects of popular worship and high community nature, that is Thien Hau Thanh Mau, Quan Thanh De Quan, Phuc. Duc Chinh Than, Confucius, Jade Emperor God, Dinh Phuc Tao Quan, Tho Dia Gia and most importantly, not to mention the Ancestor worship.

In 2007, Tran Hong Lien (editor), published "*Chinese Culture in Ho Chi Minh City*", researching the cultural characteristics of the Chinese in Ho Chi Minh City through cultural forms. tangible and intangible culture, including expressions in many fields such as culture - art, belief - religion, education, sports, painting... This is a comprehensive and comprehensive work on the cultural characteristics of the Chinese in Ho Chi Minh City, along with previous works that have helped us gain all the knowledge important and necessary when studying the Chinese people in Ho Chi Minh City.

Author Marcel Granet with the work "*La religion des chinois*", published in Paris, in 1951, wrote about the religious-religious activities of the Chinese. The work helps the author have a comparison with the religious beliefs of the Chinese in Ho Chi Minh City.

French author Jean Michel de Kermadec with "*Aspect Chinois de Cholon et Saigon*", published in 1956, describes the temples in Cholon, including architecture, decoration, worship and rituals, this is the original source material to help the author visualize the appearance of the Chinese belief establishments in the early years of the twentieth century.

In 2007, the work edited by Yuko Mio called "*Cultural Encounters between people of Chinese origin and local people: case studies from the Philippines and Vietnam*" published by the Institute of Asian and African Languages and Cultures, University of Tokyo, with a research paper by Satohiro Serizawa: "*The Fujian Chinese and the Buddhist temples in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam*". The article deals in-depth with a Chinese community in Ho Chi Minh City and their places of worship.

There are also many different works that refer to the fusion of Chinese and Vietnamese beliefs in different aspects. However, in general, the works are still mentioned sporadically, mainly in terms of one-way effects without clarifying the interaction.

Research Method

Method and Data

Articles on the theoretical basis of Marxism-Leninism, ideology Ho Chi Minh and the Party's viewpoints, lines and policies of the State of Vietnam on religion. The practical basis of the article is to analyze the process of fusion of Vietnamese and Chinese beliefs in Ho Chi Minh City.

Based on the theory of dialectical materialism and historical materialism of the Marxism-Leninism, the article uses specific methods: method analysis, synthesis, methods of data collection and processing. At the same time, there is inheriting research results related to the topic of the article

Results and Discussion

Overview of the Chinese settlement process in Ho Chi Minh City

In the middle of the seventeenth century, China's political situation had many changes, the Ming dynasty collapsed and the Manchu Dynasty was established. The movements of "Anti-Qing sentiment" were suppressed in turn, many Chinese groups in these movements sailed down to Southeast Asia to seek refuge and find new lands. Along with the Vietnamese force, at this time, the Chinese people also set foot in Gia Dinh, teaming up with the communities that had settled here before, breaking the land, setting up a market, and building this land. become rich and crowded. In 1679, the former Ming general, Longmen General Duong Ngan Dich and deputy general Hoang Tien, and General Cao Loi Liem, Tran Thuong Xuyen and deputy general Tran An Binh, brought soldiers and families of more than 3,000 people to the sea mouth. Tu Dung (Hue) "please be a servant" to Lord Nguyen. Le Quy Don wrote about this event as follows: "The 4th year of honoring Vinh Tri (1679), the escaped servant of the Ming Dynasty was General Duong Ngan Dich, General Duong Ngan Dich, brought more than 500 warships, 3,000 troops parked outside. Tu Dung pool gate, Da Nang, afraid of Thuan Hoa, dare not enter.

The general guarding at Tu Dung sent out troops to ask, Ngan Dich raised the white flag to beg for surrender. Phuc Tan immediately went to Cambodia and told the king of Cambodia to divide the land for Ngan Dich to stay at My Thu gate, to become brothers, and to bring sacrifices every year” (Don, 2007, tr.27-28). Tran Thuong Xuyen sent his army and ships to Can Gio gate, down and stationed at Ban Lan (Bien Hoa), a part stopped in the Saigon area to explore land and set up markets. Cho Lon area was slowly formed. By 1778, the major centers of the Chinese in the South (Ha Tien, My Tho, Cu Lao Pho) were devastated by war (the war between Tay Son and Nguyen Anh, the Siamese attack). Flowers pulled to Cho Lon. As Francis Garnier put it: “These Chinese people left Cu Lao Pho (in Bien Hoa) and went up the Tan Binh river and chose the location that is now Cho Lon. This construction began around 1778. They called this new residence Tai-Ngon or Tin-gan. The Annamites changed that name to Saigon...” (Giau, Đang & Binh, 1987, p.165). Tsai Maw Kuey also shared the same opinion: "The merger of the Chinese refugees in Thanh Ha and the inhabitants of Minh Huong village gave birth to the city of Cholon (1778)" (National History of the Nguyen Dynasty, 2001, p.112,131). Cho Lon at that time belonged to Tan Long canton, Tan Binh district, of Phien Tran. Towards the end of the 18th century (about 1795), the Cho Lon area was noted on the map with the name "Bazar Chinois" (Guest street). This further proves the large concentration of Chinese people (mainly) in this area.

In the early 19th century, Nguyen Anh defeated the Tay Son movement to establish the Nguyen dynasty (1802). In order to repay those who helped him during his exile, the founding king of the Nguyen Dynasty had many very open policies towards the Chinese. As noted by Tsai Maw Kuey: "These people enjoy the same rights as the Vietnamese, but do not have the same obligations, because they are exempted from military service and periodical services". The Chinese community in Cho Lon is even more favored. Chinese merchants residing in Cho Lon, if guaranteed by commune chief Minh Huong, are entitled to preferential rights. By the 13th year of Gia Long (1815), with the approval of Senior Minister Trinh Hoai Duc, the Chinese in Minh Huong Gia Thanh were allowed to use rituals, customs, and ethnic languages of different localities is divided into autonomous states, including: Quang Trieu, Phuoc Thien, Trieu Chau, Hainan and the He people, called five states. The mayor is elected by the merchants and manages the Association's affairs, mediates disputes in the Chinese community, and collects taxes to pay to the local government.

In the 19th century, the French created favorable conditions for the Chinese to settle in Saigon and Cho Lon. In 1949, the Communist Party of China liberated the Chinese, some of the Kuomintang fled to Taiwan, Hong Kong and some to Vietnam (mostly in Saigon) to work for the Chinese community here. more and more numerous. Thus, from the 17th century to the middle of the 20th century, the Chinese came to Vietnam in four large waves, by waterway and by road. The two largest settlements are in Gia Dinh, Thanh Ha village in Bien Hoa and Minh Huong village in Cho Lon (Lien, 2007, p.11), of which the Cho Lon area (districts 5, 6, Ho Chi Minh City) Minh is now the most numerous). According to the Census, the Vietnamese population of Chinese people in 1979 was 935,047 people, in 1989 there were 900,185 people, in 1999 there were 862,371 people. By 2009, data from the Population and Housing Census showed that there were 823,071 Chinese in Vietnam, present in all 63 provinces and cities. In which, in Ho Chi Minh City, there are 414,045 people, accounting for 50.3% of Chinese people in the country (General Statistics Office, 2009). Currently, in Ho Chi Minh City, the Chinese are present in most of the districts, most concentrated in districts 5, districts 6 and districts 11 (District Party Committee - People's Committee of District 5, 2000, p.40.)

The fusion of Chinese and Vietnamese religious beliefs in Ho Chi Minh City

In the process of coming to Vietnam to live, people from China, especially in the southern region (Guangdong, Fujian, etc.) to settle down have gained some basic advantages, contributing to promoting the process. their community's integration into the Vietnamese community. That is the proximity in terms of geographical location, natural conditions, similarities in culture; similarity in hydro-climate environment; a long settlement process that leads to a mixed marriage; policy of the State of Vietnam towards overseas Chinese and Chinese. Those are the factors that create cultural encounters, especially beliefs, with the close proximity and easy interference between the two communities. The process of coexistence between the Vietnamese and the Chinese over the centuries has formed in the beliefs of the Chinese many forms of cultural exchange, demonstrating the process of integration of the Chinese community into the Vietnamese community. These manifestations can be seen in many forms: architecture, decoration, rituals, worshiped gods, offerings, festivals... The harmony of Chinese and Vietnamese cultures in Religious beliefs in Ho Chi Minh City are expressed in many different aspects.

Belief in worshipping Thien Hau Thanh Mau

Most of the Chinese in Ho Chi Minh City worship Thien Hau Thanh Mau. Wherever there are Chinese immigrants to settle down, there is a temple to worship Thien Hau. Legend has it that Thien Hau Thanh Hau came from Chau Mi, Bo Dien district, Fujian province, the girl surnamed Lam was a person who attained enlightenment, displayed miraculous powers to help people in distress at sea. According to Tsai Maw Kuey: she gave spiritual help to the Song dynasty emissaries in distress at sea, in the Ming and Qing dynasties she received many epiphanies to help the imperial fleet, and was awarded the title "Blessed God", "Queen" and in the Kangxi

Dynasty (Qing Dynasty) she was conferred the title of Holy Mother. People worship her as "Holy Mother", "Thien Mother".

In Ho Chi Minh City, the belief of worshipping Thien Hau Thanh Mau is associated with the migration and settlement process of the Chinese at the end of the 18th century: Thien Hau Temple (Tue Thanh Hoi Quan) was built in 1760, another shrine (Ha Chuong Hoi Assembly Hall) the year of construction is unknown, but a pair of ancient tombs of the Temple recorded the year of restoration "Gia Khanh Ky Ty Nien" (1809), so the temple was built before 1809 (Lien, 1998, p. 462), other Thien Hau shrines date back later. If in China, Thien Hau is worshiped in the form of a painting of "a woman sitting on a wave or a cloud, or only sitting on a throne" (Henri, 2000, p.260), then in Ho Chi Minh City The Chinese worship the statue of Thien Hau, which is solemnly placed in the main hall, dedicated to the "Thien Hau Cung". She is honored as one of the first gods of the community "Thien Hau is dressed in a dark robe, embroidered with brocade, and dressed in royal clothes" (Institute of Social Sciences in Ho Chi Minh City, 1990, p. 18). In addition to the establishments Thien Hau Thanh Mau is the god, the Chinese also worship Thien Hau at the shrines of Quan Thanh De Quan (Ong Temple - Nghia An Hoi Quan, Ong Lang Pagoda - On Lang Hoi Quan). Not only worshipping at the communal temple, Thien Hau Thanh Mau is also worshiped at home with other gods.

It can be seen that the function of Lady Thien Hau has changed, because it comes from the need to find spiritual support in the face of many storms when leaving the homeland, but people worship Thien Hau Thanh Mau as a sea god (god of the sea). However, when she came to Vietnam, the function of this goddess was expanded, she became an almighty goddess, meaning the god who rules an area (ie areas where the settlement of Chinese). Vietnamese people also come to worship Ba on Tet holidays. Therefore, it can be seen that the most prominent feature of the worship of Ba Thien Hau is the culmination of the cultural interference between the two ethnic groups of China and Vietnam, and we can also affirm that she is the object of worship of the right to worship. function with the function of patronizing and guaranteeing the life of not only the Chinese, but also the Vietnamese. The Vietnamese in Ho Chi Minh City have adopted the Chinese belief of Ba worship and also look up to Ba Thien Hau as a deity of their community.

Belief in worshipping Mr. Bon

Most of the Chinese in the South have the custom of worshipping Mr. Bon. The Chinese consider Mr. Bon to be their supporter in their journey to the sea to migrate to the South. The Chinese worship Ong Bon is similar to the Vietnamese worshipping Thanh Hoang Bon Canh (who is the supporter of the community). And these two beliefs have a harmony, interference with each other for the two Chinese - Vietnamese communities in the South, as well as in Ho Chi Minh City. Therefore, the way of worship, rituals, as well as the image of Mr. Bon of the Chinese people in Ho Chi Minh City are different from other localities.

For the Chinese (and Vietnamese) in Ho Chi Minh City, Mr. Bon is also considered Tho Dia - God of Wealth. The Chinese believe that there is a god who governs the land area of the family, family, and community in which they reside. This deity is called the earth god or earth god. This means that this deity will bless us in our residence, prosperous business, and happy life, so the temple often has a couplet: "Earth energy gives birth to white jade / God comes out of gold" meaning: "Earth has the ability to produce white pearls; Gold is born from the gods". The god of wealth is the god who brings a lot of fortune to the family, so the Chinese people believe and worship. A historical figure, Pham Lai (a loyal servant of Viet Vuong Cau Tien), is also considered a god of wealth. He wholeheartedly helped King Viet Vuong in his tribulation and assisted the Vietnamese king to avenge King Ngo Phu Sai. The Chinese are an ethnic group with a knack for business, so the custom of worshipping the god of wealth has become important and popular, somewhat long in the history of beliefs. On the contrary, the Vietnamese are "agricultural" residents, so they maintain the custom of worshipping the Earth god and the belief of prosperity. At the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, the God of Earth and the God of Wealth in our country still did not clearly distinguish. In "Dai Nam Quoc yin self" (Saigon, 1895), author Huynh Tinh Cua explains that Tho god and Tai god are both "Gods of Earth, god of money" and so far the gods of Tai and Tho Dia are still living. are worshiped together as a couple, inseparable everywhere, from corporate offices, shops, homes... even on the roof of a retail cigarette cabinet by the roadside. It is worth noting that, the image of the Vietnamese god of wealth, in terms of iconography, is a variation of the Chinese god Tho Dia/Phuoc Duc. This is proof of the influence of Chinese beliefs on the Vietnamese. In fact, for the Chinese, Tu Dia is also one of the gods of wealth. In other words, also because agriculture plays an important role in history, so land, along with agricultural products born from the land, is the main wealth and property, so the god of land is also the god of wealth. In other words, because agriculture plays an important role in history, so land, along with agricultural products born from the land, is the main wealth and property, so the god of Earth is also the god of wealth. On the other hand, the Earth god has the ability to be the god of wealth because of the theory of the five elements of mutual birth: "Earth gives birth to metal". According to this concept, Phuc Duc Chinh Than (Earth Dia) is identified with God of Wealth. Therefore, the Chinese, using the image of an old man with a white beard, white hair, wearing a shirt, hat, and holding gold in one hand, given to the people, that is the image of the popular God of Fortune, Duc Chinh, and worshiped in the temples. The

worshiping site of Tho Dia, the God of Wealth of Chinese and Vietnamese people in District 5 (Trang, 2008, p.112).

However, it is also important to note that the Chinese gods of Earth are diverse, even complex, because they are referred to according to different theories. At the places of worship, it is also understood with many meanings, depending on the indigenous people of that area. For example, the God of Earth who governs the whole Cho Lon area (Saigon old town) is worshiped in Nhi Phu Hoi Quan. According to the altar of worship, the official name of the god is "The Second Palace of Dai Ba Cong Temple", which is identified with Mr. Bon (本頭公) (Bon Tou Gong - Chau Dagan). On the fresco hanging in front of the main hall of Nhi Phu Mieu, it is written that "Wu Tho Dia wild" (吾土也) (I am Tu Dia here), on it is written the year of manufacture in the reign of King Dong Tri (1861-1875) of the Qing Dynasty, China: "Dong Tri Giap Ty Year of the Year of the Rat" (吉春仲年子甲治同) (Good day, February, Dong Tri Year of the Rat - 1864) and the main function of the god is to protect fortune. This shows that this is the god of Fortune, god of Earth and god of humanity; but in fact, this is a god of the "five earths": the god of the land, protecting the warehouses of goods, more broadly understood as the market and more broadly, the Cholon/Bazar Chinois region. In the concentrated Chinese settlements (neighborhoods, alleys, streets...) there are shrines to worship Tho Dia/Phuoc Duc, the main god. At the same time, in worship establishments also worship Tho Dia/Phuoc Duc main god, in order to protect temples and shrines next to the mandarin gate. At the private house, the god of the land of the house (worshiped right in front of the door, a simple altar, placed close to the porch floor) is identified as "The Gate of the Earth to receive the Tai God". So the function of this Earth god is to bring fortune to the homeowner.

The image of Mr Bon, in the process of developing Bon's beliefs in Vietnam, has undergone a transformation, going from natural god (Tho Dia) → human god (Chau Dat Quan) → natural god (Phuoc Duc Chinh Than). This transformation has been assigned to Mr. Bon, as a natural god, as the God of Wealth who will bestow people with much fortune. This phenomenon is associated with the context of industrialization of the country, especially in Ho Chi Minh City, where the majority of Chinese are merchants residing, participating in the economic activities of the city. This belief has both shown a very profound Sino-Vietnamese cultural interference, when the Chinese have contact with the belief of Thanh Hoang Bon, a very typical scene of the Vietnamese people, the Vietnamese have an absorbing cultural change worshiping the land of the Chinese people. Dang Hoang Lan made a very subtle comment when he said: "Worshiping Mr Bon also shows that the Chinese have considered Vietnam as their homeland. This proves the trend of changing from Chinese nationals to Vietnamese citizens" (Lan, 2014).

Belief in worshiping Quan Thanh De Quan

Quan Thanh De Quan is the name of Guan Gong, a character who lived under the Three Kingdoms period of China. His real name is Quan Vu – the name Van Truong (162-219). Along with Luu Bei and Truong Phi, Quan Vu became brothers with the famous anecdote "Taoyuan three pledges". The worship of Quan Cong shows that the Chinese value loyalty and loyalty in social relationships. In Ho Chi Minh City today, the largest place to worship Quan Cong is Nghia An Assembly Hall in District 5 (also known as Ong Pagoda) of the Trieu Chau people. Here, Quan Cong is worshiped in the middle of the main hall. According to most of the left and right, there are Quan Binh and Chau Xuong. Traditionally, Chinese people generally celebrate Guan Gong's day on the 13th day of the 1st lunar month (as Quan Cong take refuge in the three treasures), May 13 (the astral body) and the 24th day of the 6th month (as a saint). annual. However, in Nghia An Assembly Hall, the most important and most celebrated holiday is the 15th day of the first lunar month. These are really big festivals for the Chinese community in general and Chaozhou Chinese in particular. They come to offer incense to commemorate and pray for Quan Cong's blessing for health, happiness, business prosperity, favorable business...

The Chinese in Ho Chi Minh City revere Quan Cong as their special mode of existence in a foreign land, although today, that cult as well as sacrificial activities are somewhat refined. much simplified and with some changes due to the conditions in the new land and the mixture with Vietnamese culture. However, all that, still does not lose the value of the worship of Quan Cong, but on the contrary, is still very developed with its own identity.

The Chinese people respect Quan Thanh De Quan very much, he is a symbol of faith, justice, loyalty and compassion for people, they also consider him a god who saves lives, blesses business and trade, so he is still famous. worship in the home in the most solemn place. Along with Quan Cong, there are also Tho Dia, Than Tai, Ong Tao, Cuu Thien Huyen Nu, the gods who save lives are also worshiped by the Chinese at home and at work, showing the cultural exchange between Vietnam and China.

Belief in worshiping Thien Quan Tu Phuoc

Influenced by Taoism, the worship of heaven has been integrated into folk beliefs by the Chinese. However, if in Taoism, people worship the Jade Emperor God (帝上玉) as the supreme king of the sky, the lord of the heavens, on the contrary, in folk beliefs, the Chinese () and Vietnamese people) simply called "God". In Ho Chi Minh City, the God altar (Thien altar) is placed high in front of the main door of each house, while in the countryside, it is placed in the yard. The layout is quite simple: includes an incense burner, a vase of flowers

(may or may not have two small glasses of water for offerings). The tablet has four characters "Thien Quan Tu Phuoc (Phuc)" (福賜官天), meaning "God bless". Usually, every evening, the householder will burn incense and pray to God regularly. On Tet holiday, it is possible to order some more fruits and change the water to offer. It can be seen in the worship of "Thien Quan Tu Phuoc", which is a manifestation of the fusion with indigenous communities, including the Vietnamese, and folklore an ancient religion of the Chinese. Looking at the surface of this belief, one may mistakenly think that it is merely the reception and transformation of Taoism, but in fact, the content of this belief is rooted in the ancient beliefs of mankind. kind, which is nature worship. Because the Jade Emperor God is originally the god in Heaven, has the power to govern and control all things in the universe, so worshipping him is worshipping nature. In the worship of God of the Chinese people in Ho Chi Minh City, we see a close blend between two forms of belief and religion. It is an expression of flexibility, creative thinking in the worldview of the Chinese and the fusion of Chinese and Vietnamese beliefs about worshipping God in Ho Chi Minh City.

Beliefs of worshipping ancestors and clans

Around the world, Ancestor worship beliefs exist in many different cultures of countries and ethnic groups. Worshipping grandparents and parents is also an expression of the perception of the universe and human outlook of the Chinese and Vietnamese. The concept of life and death is clearly expressed through the worship of ancestors. Ancestor worship is also an expression of divinity, reflecting descendants' belief in the existence of their grandparents' souls, "...even though they have gone to eternity, there is still a mystical connection mysterious and strong with children and grandchildren, helping and instructing them to avoid evil and keep good..." (Lien, 2002, p.41).

Regarding the origin, most researchers agree that the origin of Ancestor worship is the concept of Animism (also known as Soul Onlyism/Animism). This is a concept (or phenomenon) "...not only common, but seems to be an inevitable stage in the development of human culture, when animal humans have become social people" . In addition, the influence of Taoism makes people more firmly grounded in believing that death in the earthly world will begin a new life in another world; The concept of "soul" was born, or in other words, death means "living" in a different environment.

In most Chinese families, regardless of wealth or poverty, ancestral worship is always the most focused spiritual space with an altar placed on high. According to the author's observations, most Chinese families will worship Quan Am Bodhisattva and Quan Thanh De Quan on the ancestral altar and burn incense daily. On the altar, a plate of fruits and vegetables will be displayed on Tet holidays of the year. Ancestor worship is very focused by the Chinese, the ancestors altar is placed in the most solemn position in the house, in the middle of the living room, worship room or upstairs, upstairs.

With a nostalgic heart for the dead along with the wish that they also have a community life like the living, the Chinese of all dialect groups have their own graveyards.

Unlike other ethnic groups, the Chinese not only worship their ancestors in the family, but moreover, they also built them from the road to worship the same ancestor who enlightened the family. According to statistics, there are more than 50 Chinese street words in Ho Chi Minh City alone (Lan, 2014, p.90-97). The clan leader will be the one responsible for taking care of the road. They are the moderators of their death ceremonies. The operating budget is based on the arbitrary amount of contributions from families. Through such anniversaries, the solidarity of the members is tightened and more connected.

In the context of leaving to a new land, their ancestor worship proves to be an already tight community institution, now even tighter. The spirit of mutual love and affection has been clearly expressed by the Chinese. In addition to worshipping the ancestors of the family in the street, the spirit of solidarity and mutual love of the Chinese in Ho Chi Minh City can also be seen in the way the Chinese state was established. Accordingly, it can be understood: "The State is a form of social organization born from the survival needs of Chinese immigrants, whose activities are to support the members of the State in material and spiritual matters..." (Lien, 2015). Therefore, with the belief of worshipping ancestors and families of the Chinese in the South, the two biggest cultural values we see are the spirit of solidarity, mutual affection, mutual love and the spirit of "Drinking water" , remember the source". These two values create a solid basis for the Chinese to preserve the traditional cultural values of their homeland, and at the same time absorb some elements of the Vietnamese community's ancestor worship beliefs. who settled in large numbers in Ho Chi Minh City.

Discussion

The Chinese came to settle in Ho Chi Minh City in the context that the Vietnamese had settled in large numbers to establish villages here, along with the Nguyen lord's policy of encouraging reclamation and establishing sovereignty in the South, the Vietnamese community Vietnam became more and more crowded. But the Chinese people have been living with the Vietnamese community, jointly exploiting the land, establishing villages, exchanging goods, setting up markets... That process of community has led to cultural interference and confusion. Religious contention occurred naturally between the two communities.

In the process of cultural exchange with the Vietnamese, the Chinese, besides worshipping Thien Hau Thanh Mau, have absorbed the Vietnamese people's Lady Chua Xu (Temple of Thien Hau - District 3), and the Temple

of God Xu Thanh Mau (Buu Quang Tinh Xa - District 6). In the Chinese belief base, the position of Ba Chua Xu is not much less than that of Thien Hau Thanh Mau. According to Tran Hanh Minh Phuong's observation: 88% of Chinese people come to Thien Hau Temple - District 3, know and come to Ba Chua Xu (Phuong, 2003, p.66). It can be said that this is the Vietnamese god who is revered by the Chinese the most compared to other gods. Phan Thi Yen Tuyet said: "The Vietnameseization factor in Chinese folk belief establishments is also many, the most typical is the Ba Chua Xu belief in Chau Doc. This belief strongly penetrates into the temple system of many Chinese temples and shrines. Nowadays, where this belief is located, there are a lot of people coming to worship. The worship of more Lady Chua Xu Chau Doc is clearly a need of the Chinese residents" (Tuyet, 2002, p.65). The Chinese do not care much about the origin of the deity from which nation, only believe that she is very devoted, always bringing blessings to those who respect her. At Thien Hau Temple (Nguyen Thi Minh Khai Street, District 3), if the main nave of the main shrine worships Thien Hau Thanh Mau, the central space of the back hall is dedicated to worshiping Ba Chua Xu, equally dignified. The worship of Ba Chua Xu in Thien Hau Temple in Ho Chi Minh City comes from the needs of the elderly Chinese class, who do not have the conditions to go on pilgrimage in Chau Doc as before. To create an absolute belief in the folk, the Chinese also created the legend that Ba Chua Xu is worshiped in Ho Chi Minh City as the sister of Ba Chua Xu Chau Doc. According to the survey results in 2010, 52.9% of Chinese people in Ho Chi Minh City worship Ba Chua Xu Chau Doc (Bang, 2005, p.329)

In addition, the Chinese people's belief in worshiping God is expressed through the altar of Thien Quan Tu Phuoc or the altar of Thien Dia Father and Mother, which also shows a profound Chinese-Vietnamese cultural fusion. The altar of Thien Quan Tu Phuoc is sometimes worshiped at home or in a temple. If at home, the altar in front of the house is like the Thien table of the Vietnamese people, but it is not built in the yard, but the altar is built into the front wall of the house. People buy the church, then drill the wall to catch it. On that shrine, there is an incense burner, three water bottles, a flower arrangement, and sometimes a salt and rice jar on either side. Inside is a tablet with four words Thien Quan Tu Phuoc. Or more simply, people buy this tablet to catch it on the wall, below the tablet there is a bottle of incense and it's done. When making offerings, place the offerings on the ground. The altar of Thien Dia, the Mother of God, is often placed in the temple to offer sacrifices to heaven and earth whenever there is a ceremony in the temple. The Chinese form of worshiping God is sometimes a pavilion to worship the Jade Emperor in the main hall of a temple. Because, the people of Ho Chi Minh City believe that: The Jade Emperor is God, he has unlimited power in deciding the blessings for the world. "In temples, the Jade Emperor statue is often depicted as a man sitting with his feet down on the throne, majestic and majestic with a calm, holy face, wearing a peaceful hat and wearing a long coat. a gate, an ivory picker, a letter, or a precious jewel" (Hai, 2003).

In particular, the fusion of Chinese-Vietnamese beliefs in Ho Chi Minh City is clearly reflected in the traditional beliefs that both Chinese and Vietnamese people admire, which is the ancestor worship belief. In the South, the Chinese group appeared almost at the same time as the process of establishing villages by Vietnamese residents - around the middle of the seventeenth century. The religious heritages of worship carried by the ancestors of the Chinese people are now easily found in the daily life of Vietnamese people in Ho Chi Minh City. Honoring parents, grandparents, ancestors is the spirit and consciousness of Vietnamese people since ancient times. When Confucianism penetrated into Vietnamese society, it contributed to enhancing, systematizing and deepening ancestor worship; The rituals of worshiping the death anniversary and funeral are adapted from Confucianism. Filial piety has been raised to filial piety. Confucianism has clear and strict regulations on ancestor worship, funerals, as in the family the youngest son (in fact, in the North and Central region is the eldest son, different from the South), has the right to inherit property, incense fire and at the same time also have the obligation to worship parents, grandparents, ancestors. Incense fields are not mortgaged or sold. Thus, the content and rites of the ancestor worship of the Vietnamese people in general and the Vietnamese in Ho Chi Minh City in particular are imbued with the spirit of Confucianism, because respect is a long-standing tradition of Vietnamese culture. agricultural culture in the South, so when receiving Confucianism, even though Confucianism has been transformed many times, the Vietnamese people were most interested in the word "meaning" and the word "human".

However, the belief in Ancestor worship has been absorbed and refracted through indigenous cultural factors, that spirit has changed in accordance with the consciousness of the Vietnamese people in the South (and Ho Chi Minh City), as the eldest son converted to the youngest son. Vietnamese people worship their ancestors without restraint, strictly according to Confucian norms. On the contrary, it is simple, ordinary and associated with the life of each family, hamlet. The form of worship is also rich, but simple, suitable for each family situation, its main content is to promote sincerity and gratitude to those who have gone before, creating a life for the next generation...

In general, although influenced by Chinese Confucianism quite deeply, there are similarities in the quintessence of Southern agricultural culture, but the Vietnamese ancestor worship beliefs in Ho Chi Minh City still have certain characteristics. specific characteristics, bearing the cultural identity of Vietnam. Not only influenced by Confucianism, the Vietnamese ancestor worship beliefs here are also deeply influenced by Taoist thought. In the

ancestor worship of the Vietnamese people in Ho Chi Minh City, offerings such as wine, votive paper or when making offerings have the colors of Taoism. the word "Bong Lai fairy scene", or when dying is considered to be rid of the dust, return to the fairy realm "go back to the fairy" (Son, 2015)... Thus, it can be said that the mystery and escapism of Taoism contributed to making the sense of ancestors more sacred, creating a more attractiveness in the ancestor worship of the Vietnamese people in the South, as well as in old Saigon and Ho Chi Minh City now.

Conclusion

Since Lord Nguyen established Gia Dinh palace in 1698 (later Saigon - Ho Chi Minh City), the Vietnamese and the Chinese lived together, contributing to the formation of the most dynamic development land. of Vietnam in the future. More than 300 years of history have created a connection and interference between the two communities of China - Vietnam in various fields, from economy to society and culture. In the field of culture, there has been a process of religious fusion between the two communities of China - Vietnam, which is reflected in the system of gods, worship facilities, festivals, and ancestor worship, lineage...forming a unique cultural feature of Ho Chi Minh City compared to other localities of Vietnam.

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